

SCHOOL ORGANIZATION CLIMATE AND EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE ON TEACHER BURNOUT WITH SELF EFFICACY AS INTERVENING VARIABLE TO STATE HIGH SCHOOLS' TEACHERS IN TEBING TINGGI, INDONESIA

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Abstract:

Teachers are human resources in the world of education who possess a significant role. However, the issue of teacher burnout has been concerning, thus, a good management of human resources is needed so that the teachers do not experience this. One noticeable reason for the teacher's burnout phenomenon is the school climate that is not conducive and does not support them in their work. In addition, emotional intelligence and high self-efficacy possessed by a teacher can be a factor influencing the burnout. This study aims to analyze the effect of school organizational climate and emotional intelligence on teacher burnout with self-efficacy as intervening variable to state high schools' teachers in Tebing Tinggi. The population in this study was teachers in Tebing Tinggi state high schools, as many as 259 teachers. Using the Slovin formula, a sample of 80 teachers was obtained. Path analysis was used as a data analysis as well as proportional random sampling for sampling techniques. The results showed that the school organizational climate and emotional intelligence had a partially negative and significant effect on teacher burnout. Self-efficacy had a partially positive and insignificant effect on teacher burnout. School organizational and emotional intelligence climate have also direct effects on teacher burnout through self-efficacy.

Keywords: emotional intelligence, school organizational climate, self-efficacy and teacher burnout

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1. Introduction

One of the supporting factors in advancing the world of education is the teacher quality. According to Republic of Indonesia Law Number 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers, said that "*Teachers are professional educators with the main task of educating, teaching, guiding, directing, training, assessing and evaluating students either in early childhood education, formal education, basic education and secondary education*". Therefore, teacher empowerment must be considered as a sustainable program in order to improve the quality of education. This is also related to the fact that teacher is a humanitarian profession that has a significant role and has a very important position in the world of education. The teacher is a role model that can be a looking glass for students in terms of behaviors. This somehow results in a teacher being demanded to look impeccable in front of his students, both in terms of knowledge, skills and behavior.

According to Kleiber and Ensman in the latest bibliography which contains 2496 publications on burnout cases in Europe, it shows that the teaching profession occupies the second position in terms of jobs which is vulnerable to burnout, with a percentage of 32% (Prestiana and Purbandini, 2012). Then a study conducted by the Department of Public Health at the Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia Health Center (PPUKM) which concludes that a teacher profession was fourth in terms of work that could cause stress, with a percentage of 45.8% (Rohaidah, 2015). Then a study conducted by Monash University showed that one out four teachers experienced almost depressed emotions that could cause burnout to the teacher. In addition, the findings of a study conducted in 2002 on 617 primary and secondary school teachers in Victoria and New State Wales Australia showed that as many as 27% teachers would experience fatigue or have experienced fatigue (Marshall, 2013). In relation to this, it can be concluded that the teaching profession is one occupation that is prone to stress and can cause burnout. Wardhani (2012) explains that burnout can be experienced by someone who works in the education sector (teacher) because teacher faces demands from students who have learning disabilities, low success rates or grades, and lack of adequate appreciation to their performance. In addition, according to Widiastuti and Astuti (2008), burnout appears as a response to excessive, repetitive, and difficult condition to overcome work stress, which will lead individuals to experience worse conditions that result in apathy, cynicism, frustration, and withdrawal.

However, it is believed that all tasks and responsibilities of a teacher can be carried out well if the teacher has high self-efficacy. This is consistent with the research conducted by Betoret (2009) which shows that the stress felt by teachers will have an impact on the symptoms of burnout, but there are factors that can overcome the level of stress felt by the teacher, namely self-efficacy. Strong self-efficacy possessed by the teacher, will foster a more positive attitude towards work and can help make the teacher's feelings composed particularly in completing difficult tasks and activities. On the contrary, teachers who doubt their abilities will feel that their responsibility is

problematic. Self-efficacy is not always related to the ability of an actual person to do a certain task, but rather emphasizes the extent to which the person feels and thinks that he is able to succeed in performing the task. Self-efficacy does not coincidentally arise in a person because it can develop in the individual through observations of the consequences of the actions performed (Prestiana, 2012).

Sumarsono (2012) suggests that one element that relates to teacher performance in schools is the school climate. This school climate prominently affects the performance of principals, teachers, and staff in schools because the school climate can affect to the achievements of school employees or in contrast, cause employees in schools to be less effective in working together to achieve the vision and mission of the school. The school organizational climate can be in the form of mutual respect between individuals from each person in the school, such as the relationship between teachers and students, teachers with teachers, students with students, and teachers with principals, and so on. A teacher must also have good emotional intelligence in order to reduce the occurrence of burnout. If a teacher does not have good emotional intelligence, then he will not be able to overcome or manage his own emotions, especially when he is experiencing a problem while he is required to teach students well. Thus, the possibility of these teachers will be more easily exposed to stress, and if he can't handle stress well, it will cause emotional exhaustion. Emotional intelligence can be used to identify and manage one's emotions, including the ability of someone to use their emotions in order to solve problems, regulate, and express emotions.

Adawiyah (2013) found a significant negative relationship between emotional intelligence and burnout trends. Avionela and Fauziah (2016) also argue that there is a significant and negative relationship between emotional intelligence and burnout. In addition, research conducted by Puspitasari and Handayani (2014) shows that there is a significant and negative relationship between the levels of self-efficacy of teachers with a level of burnout in teachers. Pangestu (2017) also showed that there is a negative and significant relationship between self-efficacy against burnout. On the other hand, Imaniar and Sularso (2016) state that burnout has significant and positive impact on emotional intelligence, and burnout has not significant and positive impact on self-efficacy. Pandean, et al. (2018) study resulted in the finding that there is a positive but not significant relationship between organizational climate and job burnout.

2. Literature Review

2.1 School Organization Climate

According to Suharsaputra (2013) the school climate is the result of media interaction in school organizations. In addition, the school climate can also be interpreted as the situation between teachers in schools. If the climate is healthy, career planning and teacher placement can be completed in good health. In opposition, if the climate is unhealthy, such as feudalistic, making a gang, full of intrigues, stabbing each other, then the implementation of career planning will become unhealthy (Barnawi, 2012).

Antika (2016) explains that the school climate is the premise of the school through observation by using its sensory devices. From some of these explanations, it can be concluded that the school climate is a condition that exists around the school, both physically and non-physically which can affect the performance of school personnel, such as principals, teachers, school staff, and also students. Stringer explained the measurement of organizational climate by using several factors, which consisted of structure, standards, responsibility, appreciation, support, and commitment (Wirawan, 2007).

2.2 Emotional Intelligence

According to Goleman (2018) emotional intelligence is the ability to regulate emotional life with intelligence, maintain alignment of emotion and expression through the skill of self-awareness, self-control, self-motivation, empathy and social skills. Agustian (2012) argues that emotional intelligence is to listen to the whisperings emotional, and how important it is to utilize it as a source of information in order to understand themselves and others towards achieving a goal. From some of these opinions, it can be concluded that emotional intelligence is the ability to understand and manage their own emotions in order to face the pressure of the environment and to guide behavior in a positive direction. Goleman (2018) emotional intelligence can be grouped into five major capabilities, namely:

- 1) Recognizing self-emotion, it is an ability to recognize feelings when those feelings occur.
- 2) Managing emotions, it is the ability of individuals to handle feelings so that they can be revealed correctly or in harmony, so that balance is achieved in the individual.
- 3) Motivate yourself, this means having perseverance to refrain from satisfaction and controlling impulses, and have a positive motivation, namely enthusiasm, passion, optimism, and self-confidence.
- 4) Recognizing other people's emotions, it is the ability to recognize other people's emotions or is also called empathy. It is also associated to the ability of someone to recognize other people or care about others and to show one's empathy.
- 5) Having the ability to build relationships, it is a skill that supports popularity, leadership and success between individuals. Communication skill is a basic ability to build relationships.

2.3 Self-Efficacy

The term self-efficacy was first introduced by Albert Bandura. Bandura (1997) said "*Efficacy is a major base of action. People guide their lives by their beliefs of personal efficacy. Self-efficacy is a capability to organize and execute the course of action required to product given attainments*". According to Kahn (2011) self-efficacy is as self-confidence in the ability of oneself to carry out an action needed for the desired results. Based on these opinions, it can be concluded that self-efficacy is an attitude of confidence that is owned by a person

towards his ability to act so that he can achieve the desired results. Alwisol (2012) explains that self-efficacy or self-habitual beliefs can be obtained, changed, enhanced or reduced, through one or a combination of four sources, namely:

- 1) Experience performance, as a source, the reformation of the community has become the most influential modifier of self-efficacy. Good past performance increases efficacy expectations while failure will reduce efficacy.
- 2) Experience other people's success (vicarious experience). Efficacy will increase when observing the success of others; otherwise efficacy will decrease if observing a person whose abilities are about the same as him and turns out to be a failure.
- 3) Social persuasion. The impact of this source is limited, but in the right conditions persuasion from others can influence self-efficacy. The condition is trust in the persuasion giver, and the realistic nature of what is being persuaded for.
- 4) Emotional state. Strong emotions, fear, anxiety, stress, can reduce self-efficacy. However, an increase in emotions (which is not excessive) can increase self-efficacy. One's experience is an important source of information. According to Bandura, self-efficacy in each individual will differ from one individual to another based on three dimensions. The three dimensions are as follows (Ghufron and Risnawati, 2014):
 - a) The level dimension (magnitude), it is related to the degree of difficulty of the task when the individual feels able to do it. This component has implications for the choice of behavior that individuals will try based on expectations of efficacy at the level of difficulty of the task.
 - b) The dimension of strength, it is related to the level of strength of an individual's beliefs or expectations regarding his abilities. This dimension often has to face frustration, injury and various other obstacles in achieving a certain outcome.
 - c) Dimensions of generality. It is related to the broad field of behavior in which individuals feel confident in their abilities.

2.4 Teacher's Burnout

Burnout is a psychological term used to indicate work fatigue. The term burnout was first introduced in 1969 by Bradley, but the prominent figure who is considered the inventor of the term burnout is Herbert Freudenberger (a psychiatrist at a social service institution that handles problematic adolescents), in 1974, with his book "Burnout: The High Cost of High Achievement", which provides an illustration of those who experience the syndrome who feel like a burned-out building. A building that used to stand tall and majestic filled with various activities in it yet after being burnt, the outer frame is the only things left and seen. Likewise with someone who is affected by the same circumstances, everything from the outside still seems intact, but inside, it is empty and full of glitches. Since then, burnout terminology has developed and is used to understand a person's psychological phenomena (Imaniar and Sularso, 2016).

Widiastuti and Astuti (2008) explained that burnout in the teacher will directly affect students. Burnout will affect the enthusiasm of students to learn and result in the emergence of negative feelings among students towards the world of education. Burnout is also a major factor in low moral causes, such as truant, late work, and a strong desire to change jobs. Research on burnout in teachers has been carried out by many researchers, one of which was conducted by BA Farber who stated that burnout to teachers can be originated from student ignorance, insensitivity to school supervisors, parents who do not care, lack of public appreciation for teacher work, poor physical buildings, loss of autonomy, and inadequate salaries (Dewi, 2017). From some explanations regarding burnout in the teacher above, it can be concluded that teacher burnout is psychologically exhausted in teaching because of high demands for work, attitudes of students, school environment, or rewards received by the teacher so that it can lead to behaviors such as skipping work, does not care about students. They are also found to be less disciplined and even plan to resign or to find other jobs. Maslach et al. (2001) categorize burnout into 3 (three) dimensions, namely:

- 1) Emotional Exhaustion, it is a mood that is very fatigued in terms of emotions and physical.
- 2) Depersonalization / Cynicism, it is a negative feeling, sensitive, and withdraws from all aspects of work or lack of enthusiasm in doing the tasks and work.
- 3) Reduce Personal Accomplishment / Inefficacy, it is the tendency to give a negative assessment of the failure of the work itself, his achievements are deemed insufficient and feel lack of professionalism.

3. Research Methods

This research was conducted on teachers in state high schools in the city of Tebing Tinggi, which consisted of 4 state high schools. The population of this study was 259 teachers. They consist of Civil Servants (PNS) and non-Civil Servants (non-permanent teachers). The Slovin formula is used to determine the number of samples. Based on calculations using the Slovin formula, the number of samples obtained was 80 teachers. The researcher used proportional random sampling for sampling techniques. The data collection technique in this study is to provide a list of statements in form of questionnaires to the teachers in senior high schools of Tebing Tinggi who have become research respondents.

4. Results and Discussion

The description of the model path analysis assumption for sub-structure I is as follows:

Figure 1.1: Depiction of Assumptions of Path Analysis Sub-structure I

Based on Figure 1.1, the equation of sub-structure I can be formulated as follows: $Z = \alpha + \rho_1 X_1 + \rho_2 X_2 + \epsilon_1$. The results of the t test for sub-structure I can be seen in the table below:

Table 1.1: Test Results t Sub-structure I

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	3,907	4,955		,788	,433
1 School Organizational Climate	,388	,084	,387	4,632	,000
Emotional Intelligence	,456	,076	,499	5,972	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Self-Efficacy
 Source: Research Results, 2019 (Data Processed)

Based on the table it can be explained that:

- 1) School organizational climate variables have a value of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ that is $4.632 > 1.99$ with a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$. So it can be concluded that the climate of school organizations has a positive and significant effect on self-efficacy.
- 2) Variables of emotional intelligence have a value of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ that is $5.972 > 1.99$ with a significant value of $0,000 < 0.05$. This shows that the variable emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on self-efficacy.
- 3) The regression analysis equation model for sub-structure I, namely: $Z = 3,907 + 0,388X_1 + 0,456X_2$. The drawing of the model path assumption for sub-structure II is as follows:

Figure 1.2: Illustration of Assumptions of Sub-structural Analysis II

From Figure 1.2 we can formulate the path analysis equation for sub-structure II, namely: $Y = \alpha + \rho_3X_1 + \rho_4X_2 + \rho_5Z + \epsilon_2$. The results of the t test for sub-structure II can be seen in the table below:

Table 1.2: T Test Results Sub-structure II

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	84,967	5,947		14,289	,000
1 School Organizational Climate	-,404	,113	-,328	-3,571	,001
Emotional Intelligence	-,588	,110	-,523	-5,330	,000
Self-Efficacy	-,077	,136	-,063	-,568	,572

a. Dependent Variable: Burnout Teacher
 Source: Research Results, 2019 (Data Processed)

Based on Table 1.2, it can be explained that:

- 1) School organizational climate variables have a t_{count} greater than t_{table} which is $-3.571 > 1.99$ with a significant value of $0.001 < 0.05$. So it can be concluded that the climate of the school organization has a significant influence on teacher burnout, and it can also be seen that the organizational climate variable of the school has a negative influence on teacher burnout variables, which can be seen in the negative sign in t_{count} , which indicates that the school climate experiencing an increase, it will reduce the burnout of teachers, and vice versa, if the school's organizational climate decreases, it will increase teacher burnout.
- 2) Variables of emotional intelligence have a value of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ that is $-5.330 > 1.99$ with a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This shows that the variable emotional intelligence has a negative and significant influence on teacher burnout. If emotional intelligence increases, it will reduce teacher burnout. On the contrary, if emotional intelligence decreases, it will make teacher burnout rise.
- 3) The variable self-efficacy has a value of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ that is $-0.568 < 1.99$ with a significant value of $0.572 > 0.05$. This indicates that the variable self-efficacy has a negative and not significant effect on teacher burnout.
- 4) 4. Regression equation model for sub-structure II, namely: $Y = 84,967 - 0,404X_1 - 0,588X_2 - 0,077Z$

Based on the explanation above regarding beta path coefficient values from the test results of analysis of the first and second sub-structural (sub-structure) paths and errors (ϵ_1 and ϵ_2), the path diagram can be described as follows:

Figure 1.3: Path Diagram

Direct effect, indirect effect, and total effect between independent variables, intervening variables, and the dependent variable in this study can be seen in the following explanation:

Table 1.3: Value of Direct Influence, Indirect Effects, and Total Influence

Effect of Variables in Path Analysis	Direct Influence	Indirect Effects	Total Influence
$X_1 \rightarrow Y$	-0,404	$0,388 \times (-0,077) = -0,029$	-0,433
$X_2 \rightarrow Y$	-0,588	$0,456 \times (-0,077) = -0,035$	-0,623

Source: Research Results, 2019 (Data Processed)

From Table 1.3, it can be explained that the school organizational climate variable (X_1) can directly influence the teacher's burnout variable, which is indicated by the direct effect value of $X_1 \rightarrow Y$ variable, that is -0,388 is greater than the indirect effect of variable $X_1 \rightarrow Y$, i.e. -0,029, so it can be concluded that the two variables have a direct relationship and the relationship between variable X_1 and Y is negative. In addition, from table 1.3, it can be explained that the emotional intelligence variable (X_2) can directly influence the teacher's burnout variable, which is indicated by the direct effect of variable $X_2 \rightarrow Y$, which is -0,588 which is greater than the indirect effect of variable $X_2 \rightarrow Y$, namely -0,035, so it can be concluded that the two variables have a direct relationship and the relationship between variable X_1 with Y is negative.

5. Discussion

5.1 Effects of School Organizational Climate on Teachers Burnout

The results of the study show that the school organizational climate variables partially have a negative and significant influence on teacher burnout. This shows that if the climate of the school organization is good, then it can reduce the level of burnout of teachers. Vice versa, if the school climate is bad, the teacher's burnout level will increase. The results of this study are also in accordance with research from Kristanti (2014), Grayson and Alvarez (2008) which stated that organizational climate has a

negative influence and is significant to burnout. Burnout can occur due to organizational climate conditions. The organizational climate that is not conducive will increase the occurrence of burnout. In this study, it was shown that training, career development or promotion, and teachers' appreciation/ awards at Tebing Tinggi City senior high schools were not sufficient. Teachers have never or rarely received training that will make them feel mixed up on understanding the teaching system or curriculum and so on. If it happens for the long run, teachers will feel exhausted and also indolent to work. Lack of appreciation and rewards can also make teachers mentally worn-out. Such promotions and accolades are one of the stimuli that can create teachers eagerness to teach. With the promotion and appreciation, they will feel supported and feel that their performance valued by the superior or the school, thus, a good relationship will be generated between the superior (headmaster) and subordinates (the teacher).

5.2 Effects of Emotional Intelligence on Teachers Burnout

The results of the study of emotional intelligence on teacher burnout showed that the variable emotional intelligence has a negative and significant effect on teacher burnout variables. This means the high emotional intelligence possessed by a teacher will be able to reduce the level of teacher burnout. On the other hand, if a teacher has low emotional intelligence, the level of burnout will be high. This is in line with the research conducted by Adawiyah (2013), Avionela and Fauziah (2016) which state that there is a significantly negative relationship between emotional intelligence and burnout tendency. It shows that teacher who has emotional intelligence will be able to manage his emotions, and allows him to act more rationally and without doubt won't experience burnout. Research conducted by Widjaja, et al. (2016) also explains the same thing; it found that there is a negative relationship between emotional intelligence and the teacher burnout.

5.3 Effects of Self-Efficacy on Teachers Burnout

From the results of this study, it was found that self-efficacy had a negative and insignificant effect on teacher burnout in Tebing Tinggi state high school. This indicates that burnout can actually have less important role in self-efficacy. These findings are also reinforced by the results of a study piloted by Septianisa and Caninsti (2016) which states that there is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and burnout on teachers. This can be interpreted that the high or low self-efficacy does not determine the high or low burnout. So it can be concluded that high or low self-efficacy possessed by teachers in the state high school of Tebing Tinggi will not affect the level of burnout that the teacher will experience. This is different from the research conducted by Pangestu (2017) and also Hartawati and Mariyanti (2013), who found that there is a negative and significant relationship between teacher self-efficacy and burnout, which conclude that high efficacy (self-efficacy) can help teacher in overcoming various pressures and obstacles encountered in school so that it can minimize stress and even prevent the onset of fatigue in the teacher (teacher burnout).

5.4 Effect of Climate of School Organizations on Teachers' Self-Efficacy

The results of the study indicate that the organizational climate has a positive and significant influence on teacher self-efficacy. This also shows that the good organizational climate in schools will improve the teacher's self-efficacy. On the contrary, if the school climate is low, the self-efficacy of the teacher will also decrease. This is in line with the research conducted by Irti, et al (2013) which demonstrates that there is a positive and significant relationship between organizational climate and self-efficacy. Stringer (2002) also explains that organizational climate is considered a flexible structure, gives freedom in decision making, emphasizes rewards for worthy work, encourages challenges to set goals, encourages warmth, a sense of pride and the possibility of minimizing stress, because school climate can facilitate achieving employee goals that will make employees feel confident that they can improve their abilities.

5.5 Effect of Emotional Intelligence on Teachers' Self-Efficacy

From the results of the study, it can be seen that emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on self-efficacy. This is consistent with the research conducted by Prastadila and Paramita (2013), and Islami (2013) which shows that there is a positive and significant correlation between emotional intelligence and teacher self-efficacy. It can be said that the high emotional intelligence of a teacher will increase their self-efficacy. On the contrary, teacher's low emotional intelligence will affect to low teacher's self-efficacy. Boyatzis, et al. (2002) explained that someone who has emotional intelligence will have self-confidence where he will have strong beliefs about his values and abilities. When a person has strong beliefs about his own abilities, it will influence his views particularly in completing tasks and generating performance that affects his life; this can be called self-efficacy.

5.6 The Effect of School Organizational Climate on Teacher's Burnout through Self-Efficacy

The results showed that the school organizational climate had a negative and direct influence on teacher burnout through self-efficacy, which meant that a good school organizational climate would directly be able to minimize the occurrence of burnout in the teacher. This is in line with research conducted by Asi (2013) which states that the organizational climate has a direct and negative influence on burnout. Burnout can occur due to organizational climate conditions. Organizational climate that is not conducive will increase the occurrence of burnout. According to Stringer (2002) the possibility of organizational climate can be used to minimize stress, because the organizational climate is able to facilitate the achievement of employee goals, it will make employees feel confident that they can improve their abilities. Prolonged stress will cause depression and if this lasts long, it will make a person experience burnout.

5.7 Effects of Emotional Intelligence on Teacher's Burnout through Self-Efficacy

The results showed that emotional intelligence had a negative and direct effect on teacher burnout through self-efficacy. This shows that high emotional intelligence from a teacher can directly reduce burnout. Barari and Jamshidi (2015) suggested that emotional intelligence mediated by the role of self-efficacy had an indirect and negative relationship to burnout. In addition, according to Ema (2004) with the presence of emotional intelligence, a person will have self-regulation to control himself so as not to be affected by excessive workload that might develop into a burnout tendency. Burnout circumstances appear not only influenced by the condition of the organization, but is the result of the interaction between the condition of the organization and individual characteristics, such as the emotional conditions possessed by that person.

6. Conclusion

Based on the results of the research and discussion described earlier, some conclusions are taken as follows:

- 1) The school organizational climate has a negative and significant influence on burnout to teachers of state high schools in city of Tebing Tinggi.
- 2) Emotional intelligence has a negative and significant effect on burnout to teachers of state high schools in the city of Tebing Tinggi.
- 3) Self-efficacy has a negative and insignificant effect on burnout to teachers of state high schools in the city of Tebing Tinggi.
- 4) The school organizational climate has a positive and significant effect on self-efficacy to teachers of state high schools in the city of Tebing Tinggi.
- 5) Emotional intelligence has a positive and significant influence on self-efficacy to teachers of state high schools in the city of Tebing Tinggi.
- 6) The school organizational climate has a direct effect on teacher burnout with self-efficacy as an intervening variable to teachers of state high schools in the city of Tebing Tinggi.
- 7) Emotional intelligence has a direct effect on teacher burnout with self-efficacy as an intervening variable to teachers of state high schools in the city of Tebing Tinggi.

To further improve the climate of the school organization in order to reduce teacher burnout, the school should consider holding training, career development, and appreciation for teachers. Training can be used to develop teacher competencies or skills so that they can quickly adjust to the changes that are taking place. Then career development and rewards must be carried out fairly, because career development (promotion) and awards/ appreciation show that there is support from the school for teachers who have good potential and achievements. In addition, this can also be a motivation for teachers so they are keen to improve their performance. It is also suggested for the school to provide facilities, infrastructure, and good training to help teachers adapt to the changes in science and technology in the current education sector

so that the teachers can also have better knowledge and skills. They can also adjust to overcome changes in students caused by the progress in technologies. Although self-efficacy does not play an important role in reducing the level of teacher burnout in Tebing Tinggi state high schools, teachers should improve their self-efficacy because teachers are required to be professional in any situation or circumstances. They also must have self-confidence towards their ability to complete certain tasks so that they can be good role models for their colleagues and students.

References

- Adawiyah, R. A. R. (2013). Kecerdasan Emosional, Dukungan Sosial dan Kecenderungan Burnout. *Persona: Jurnal Psikologi Indonesia*, 2(2).
- Agustian, A. G. (2012). Emotional Spiritual Quotient The ESQ Way 165. *Jakarta: Arga Publishing*.
- Alwisol. (2012). *Psikologi Kepribadian*. Malang: UMM Press.
- Antika, M. (2016). Pengaruh Gaya Belajar dan Iklim Sekolah Terhadap Hasil Belajar IPS Terpadu Siswa Kelas VIII SMP Negeri 3 Bandar Lampung Tahun Pelajaran 2015/2016. *Skripsi*, Fakultas Keguruan dan Ilmu Pendidikan, Universitas Lampung.
- Asi, S. P. (2014). Pengaruh iklim organisasi dan burnout terhadap kinerja perawat RSUD dr. Doris Sylvanus Palangka Raya. *Jurnal Aplikasi Manajemen*, 11(3), 515-523.
- Avionela, F., & Fauziah, N. (2017). Hubungan Antara Kecerdasan Emosi Dengan Burnout Pada Guru Bersertifikasi Di SMA Negeri Kecamatan Bojonegoro. *Empati*, 5(4), 687-693.
- Bandura, A. (1997). *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control*. New York : W. H. Freeman and Company.
- Barari, R., & Jamshidi, L. (2015). The effectiveness of emotional intelligence on job burnout mediated the self-efficacy among elementary teachers. *International Journal of Educational and Psychological Researches*, 1(3), 212.
- Barnawi, M. A. (2012). *Buku Pintar Mengelola Sekolah (Swasta)*. Yogyakarta: Ar-ruzz Media.
- Betoret, F. D. (2009). Self-efficacy, school resources, job stressors and burnout among Spanish primary and secondary school teachers: a structural equation approach. *Educational Psychology*, 29(1), 45-68.
- Boyatzis, R.E., Goleman, D., Hay, G. (2002). *Emotional Competence Inventory*. HayGroup.
- Dewi, R. S. (2017). Pengaruh Pelatihan Efikasi Diri Sebagai Pendidik TERHADAP Penurunan Burnout Pada Guru Di Sekolah Inklusi. *Naturalistic: Jurnal Kajian Penelitian Pendidikan dan Pembelajaran*, 1(2), 155-167.
- Ema, A. (2004). Peranan dimensi-dimensi birokrasi terhadap burnout pada perawat rumah sakit di Jakarta. *Jurnal Psyche*, 1(1), 33-46.

- Ghufron, M. N. S, Rini Risnawati.(2014). *Teori-teori psikologi*. Yogyakarta: Ar-Ruzz Media
- Goleman, D. (2018). *Emotional intelligence*. Jakarta : PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Grayson, J. L., & Alvarez, H. K. (2008). School climate factors relating to teacher burnout: A mediator model. *Teaching and teacher education*, 24(5), 1349-1363.
- Hartawati, D., & Mariyanti, S. (2013). Hubungan antara Self-efficacy dengan Burnout pada Pengajar Taman Kanak-kanak Sekolah "X" di Jakarta. *Jurnal Psikologi Esa Unggul*, 12(02).
- Imaniar, R. R. L., & Sularso, R. A. (2016). Pengaruh Burnout Terhadap Kecerdasan Emosional, Self-Efficacy, dan Kinerja Dokter Muda di Rumah Sakit dr. Soebandi. *Jurnal Maksipreneur: Manajemen, Koperasi, dan Entrepreneurship*, 5(2), 46-56..
- Irti, A., Nurtjahjanti, H., & Putra, N. A. (2013). Hubungan Antara Iklim Organisasi Dengan Self-efficacy Pada Karyawan Tetap Non-exempt PT. Bina Guna Kimia Ungaran. *Empati*, 2(3), 131-141.
- Islami, R. (2013). *Hubungan Antara Kecerdasan Emosional Dengan Efikasi Diri Guru Agama Islam (Ustadz) Dalam Pembelajaran Di Pesantren Darusy Syahadah Boyolali* (Doctoral dissertation, Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta).
- Kristanti, N. (2014). *Hubungan antara Iklim Sekolah dengan Burnout pada Guru di SMP N 2 Sukolilo, Pati* (Doctoral dissertation, Program Studi Psikologi FPSI-UKSW).
- Marshall, K. (2013). Burnout hits one in four teachers. *The Age Victoria*.
- Maslach, C., Schaufeli, W. B., & Leiter, M. P. (2001). Job burnout. *Annual review of psychology*, 52(1), 397-422.
- Pandean, P. N., Kairupan, R. K. R., & Rompas, S. (2018). Hubungan Iklim Organisasi Dan Masa Kerja Dengan Kelelahan Kerja Perawat Di Rumah Sakit Umum Gmim Bethesda Tomohon. *Jurnal Keperawatan*, 6(1).
- Tuti Pangestu, T., Dwityanto, A., & Psi, S. (2017). *Hubungan Antara Efikasi Diri Dengan Burnout Pada Perawat* (Doctoral dissertation, Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta).
- Prastadila, P., Paramita, P. P., & Psych, M. E. (2013). Hubungan antara emotional intelligence dengan self-efficacy guru yang mengajar di sekolah inklusi tingkat dasar. *Jurnal Psikologi Pendidikan dan Perkembangan*, 2(1), 1-11.
- Prestiana, N. D. I., & Purbandini, D. (2012). Hubungan antara efikasi diri (self-efficacy) dan stres kerja dengan kejenuhan kerja (burnout) pada perawat IGD dan ICU RSUD Kota Bekasi. *SOUL: Jurnal Ilmiah Psikologi*, 5(2), 1-14.
- Septianisa, S., & Caninsti, R. (2018). Hubungan Self Efficacy Dengan Burnout Pada Guru Di Sekolah Dasar Inklusi. *Journal Psikogenesis*, 4(1), 126-137.
- Stringer, R. (2002). *Leadership and Organization Climate*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- Suharsaputra, U. (2013). *Administrasi Pendidikan*. Bandung: PT Refika Aditama.
- Sumarsono, R. B. (2012). Iklim Sekolah, Komitmen Organisasi, Kepuasan Kerja, dan Kinerja Guru. *Manajemen Pendidikan*, 23(6), 532-539.
- Wardhani, D. T. (2012). Burnout di Kalangan Guru Pendidikan Luar Biasa di Kota Bandung. *Jurnal Psikologi*, 11(1), 10.

- Widjaja, M. S., Sitorus, K. S., & Himawan, K. K. (2016). Hubungan Antara Kecerdasan Emosional Dengan Kecenderungan Burnout Pada Karyawan Bagian Pemasaran. *Jurnal Psikologi Ulayat: Indonesian Journal of Indigenous Psychology*, 3(1), 18-33.
- Widiastuti, D. Z., & Astuti, K. (2008). Hubungan antara kepribadian hardiness dengan burnout pada guru sekolah dasar. *Jurnal InSight*, 6(2).
- Wirawan, N. (2007). *Budaya dan Iklim Organisasi*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.

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